

Deliverable 2.2

Policy positioning report on ecosystem gap analysis

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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC services)	
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Document Control Sheet

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Executive Summary

This report provides an in-depth gap analysis of the digital Research and Innovation needs identified through the project research. The gap analysis involved assessing the needs collected and classifying them per region (those that apply to the entire EU – SSA and those that apply to the specific pilot regions). A further deliberation was done to select the needs that related to the activities of the SEADE project. Some of those needs would be addressed through these activities (such as the learning expedition, soft landing mission, youth training program and several webinars) and the tools and services applied through these activities.

The 5 key needs summarized for the EU-SSA region included Cultural and Operational differences, funding, legal barriers and mismatches, need for enhancement of infrastructure such as reliable power and internet connectivity and software and hardware tools and the need for inclusivity and empowerment for women and youth. A further assessment showed that the question of funding is not about the lack of funding opportunities but the inadequacy in the skills for application for various funding opportunities. That is, innovators are either not aware of the funding opportunities or do not have the knowledge or skills to apply for available funding opportunities.

The main needs for Ghana were the need for mentorship programs and proper alignment of its research and innovation policies to regional and international policies. Awareness of opportunities was key for the Kenyan ecosystem while Senegal and South Africa faced problems of inadequate market linkages and unequal power dynamics respectively. In addition to this conclusion, the report shows that the West African region is highly influenced by the ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) policies. The East African region follows policies developed in Kenya and the South African region countries are independent in their policies and needs.

The key recommendations for these needs are detailed in the report for each of the needs. A highlight for cultural and operational differences was what was as **Tech to fit communities not communities to fit tech** where technology that is built should align with the communities' way of living. Several initiatives are also highlighted under each of the needs whose implementation would help to solve the need. The initiatives are under the global gateway and more specifically the implemented ICT58 projects, D4D Hub and PRIMA database of initiatives.

The Digital Youth Training program as an activity of the project will partially address the need for infrastructure through dedicated software and hardware tools for learning that would be provided to the Innovators. The Enrich in Africa platform through its current integrated services such as the marketplace, the academy and the Euroquity feature will also support some of the needs when it is applied in several activities of the project.

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List of Abbreviations

EU	European Union
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
EiA	Enrich in Africa

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1. Introduction

This deliverable builds on the needs assessment and Policies and Strategies as well as initiatives for Digital R&I ecosystem for AU-EU cooperation exercises. It provides an in-depth analysis of the needs and gives recommendations for policy and initiatives. This document is the basis for the services to be integrated into the EiA platform which innovators would be exposed to in later activities of the project.

The needs assessment, policies and strategies collection exercise involved interviews, targeted surveys and desk research activities. The gaps identified from this exercise are now aligned in this document with suitable recommendations providing a suitable policy position for each gap. Insights are also collected from ongoing activities of the project such as webinars and EiA workshops.

Over 100+ policies and strategies were collected from the desk research some of which are general and others specific to a particular technology. The policy structure is largely influenced by ECOWAS in Western Africa while East and Southern Africa are country specific. There are over 300+ initiatives directed towards digital empowerment through formulations such as the global gateway, FPI initiatives and directly through the African Union. Despite this, there are still challenges such as Socio-cultural differences, funding opportunity awareness, inadequate digital infrastructure, social inclusion and legal differences that hinder the proper R&I integration in the AU-EU ecosystem. Some statistics on this state can be shown through the graphs in the annex section.

A conclusion will follow that summarizes the gaps and the policy position. It may be of note to refer to the summary of gaps section while reading the policy position to get a proper alignment and understanding of the recommendations.

2. Summary of Gaps Identified with Research Evidence and Analysis

The needs assessment exercise collected and compiled a list of digital research and innovation gaps after a conducting a desk research, setting up targeted interviews in each of the pilot regions and a survey to gather input from Researchers, University staff, Digital Innovation Startups, Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) members, and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The gaps are categorized by region as either global or local depending on the scale of impact. The gaps identified are summarized below. A case study along with some statistics and stakeholder input is also included in the description. The details of each of the gaps and their statistical analysis and evidence can be found in the AU/EU R&I Cooperation in Digital - Stakeholder Research Outcomes report.

2.1 Global Gaps

These are gaps that apply generally to the AU-EU ecosystem. This means that the gaps are common in R&I cooperation activities in the AU-EU collaboration framework. These are summarized as below.

Cultural and Operational Differences - The way of living and working of the European and African researchers is different. Research has shown that Europeans are stricter to deadlines, employ a strict work life balance especially in their tools of communication and are keen on risk. Africans have a flexible approach to work and personal life.

Case: 'While Europeans maintain LinkedIn and email for professional communication and WhatsApp for social networking, Africans are more aligned to WhatsApp for both professional and personal networking and less inclined to LinkedIn and Email communication in their daily activities.'

The level of research and development between the two continents differs extensively. For instance, the product is more refined and advanced technologies are used in the innovations in Europe. There is also more support for innovators in Europe than in Africa. The challenges are also different.

Case: 'Gravity Incubator under Cyric in Cyprus incubates startups that work in Mobility, BioTech, Robotics, HealthTech, Marine and Agriculture. @iLabAfrica in Kenya also incubates startups in the same fields. The level of innovation output at Cyric is higher and tailored to the needs of Cyprus. While the level of innovation output of @iLabAfrica is not as high, it is still acceptable for the local context and is aligned to the needs of Kenyan society.'

There are differences in language in most European countries and in different parts of Africa. English is a widely spoken language in Europe. Most European countries speak English. However, English is only a first language in 10 of the 44 European countries. Africa is divided in the language based on colonial influence. West Africa is more inclined to French while the East and South are to English.

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Case: 'Senegal predominantly speaks French. Italy predominantly speaks Italian. In South Africa, English is the fourth most popular language after Zulu, Xhosa and Afrikaans.'

Collaboration innovation projects between Europe and Africa become complex in their execution due to cultural and operational differences. The design of the projects in the European context have a risk of failure due to the tools selected for dissemination in the African context. Solutions developed in Europe are also not directly transferable to the African continent and vice versa. Misunderstandings amongst partners and innovators in a AU-EU collaboration are prone which endangers or slows down the collaboration process.

Funding for innovators - The challenge of funding has several interpretations in the European African collaboration and Innovation ecosystem. On the African side, funding is interpreted from a point of access, awareness and level of availability. In the European context it is interpreted from a point of running cost, effort, and cash flow.

Many platforms, venture parks and communities exist to support innovators to access funding opportunities. Some of these tools have been developed through past(legacy) AU-EU initiatives such as Innowide, Euroquity and Digital Collective Africa but most innovators are unaware of these tools.

Case: 'In the presentation of the tools developed under the SEADE Digital Environment in one of the Kenyan hubs, the innovators mentioned that they were not aware of the funding tools and opportunities presented, yet they found them easy to use. These tools have been in existence from previous AU-EU initiatives for over 3 years. The innovators became aware of the opportunities through the SEADE workshop intervention.'

The funding opportunities that exist have very high competition. The ratio of funding opportunity to Innovator is low.

Case: 'For most funding opportunities available, many applications are received for a minimal number of spots available. The odds of receiving the funds are often small. Innovators give up and seek alternative ways of making a living. This has been the for National Research Fund opportunities in Kenya and Africa wide Bill and Melinda gates opportunity.'

There is limited budget for the innovators and R&I organizations that receive funding.

Case: 'African organizations mention that in most cases the implementation is in the African context with most objectives needed to be done in the African continent, yet the budget allocated to their organizations do not match the KPIs. This limits the effort they allocate to each of their tasks.'

Many European startups and SMEs have also experienced cash flow problems due to high taxes which affects the continuity of business.

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Case: 'Reports consistently show that a significant number of SMEs in Europe struggle with cash flow problems due to late payment, post-pandemic challenges and access to finance. Greece, Italy and Portugal have reported the highest cases at 59, 54 and 42 on average percent respectively.'

Information flow of funding opportunities limits the level of development of projects which limits their ability to pair with high quality innovations. The limited information on the funding opportunities requires a lot of effort from the R&I/D actors causing many to give up for alternative ventures. This decelerates innovation in a specific field. In cooperation projects, some partners choose to deliberately limit their effort due to imbalance of resources allocations. This also decelerates collaboration activities. Finally, cooperation projects stall when cash flow problems arise.

Policy and Legal Barriers - The innovation space is becoming fragmented. There are many new emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning (ML). These new technologies move faster than the policies that are required to guide their implementation.

Case: 'AI became popular in Africa and Europe during the COVID19 era. Many startups and innovators tested the technology to solve challenges in health, safety, communication and food security. Nonetheless, the AI strategy for [South Africa](#), [Kenya](#) and Europe were released in 2025. Ghana and Senegal are yet to release their AI strategy and policies, yet innovations in this field are progressing. Africa in general through the African Union has also made efforts to introduce the [Continental AI strategy](#) to guide general implementations of AI in the continent.'

Most European countries are slower in adopting the emerging technologies, yet the African countries are more open and easily tested and implement them with less consideration for policy. The laws on data security and privacy are stricter in Europe than in Africa.

Case: 'Kenya implemented the Fintech innovation on mobile money, M-pesa in 2007. Many African countries including Ghana, Senegal and South Africa have now followed suit with MoMo, Wari and VodaPay respectively. Most of Europe still relies on cash and credit card payments and the traditional banking system. The strict data security and privacy policies impede the adoption of these technologies. Additionally, Kenya tried to apply the same system of Mpesa in the UK before Brexit, and it failed.'

Policy is linked to red tapes. Policy brings structure in organizations which is dependent on human capital and the speed and will of an individual to process information. These red tapes either slow down or completely stop the execution of an innovation task. At continent level, Europe is known for more red tapes but are more efficient in communication which ensures higher rate of task completion. Africa is flexible on the rules but where policy applies the system easily fails. This applies to organizations also. Therefore, this brings challenges in cross-border communication.

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Case: 'Most AU-EU cooperation projects have had challenges with implementation. Reports show that EU partners share many emails that are unreplied in cases where they need an output in the African pilot. This model of working is successful in the EU and not in Africa. DeKUT Innovators club in Kenya is within DeKUT university. All the activities of the club are governed by the University policies. The club has reported cases of payment delays, IP processing challenges (10 percent of all innovations output are automatically allocated to the University), and infrastructure limitations.'

Africa is moving faster in the uptake and adoption of emerging technologies. Many new technologies are easily tested by innovators in Africa. Aligning the use of these technologies in the two continents becomes a challenge. Direct transfer of the solutions between the two continents is often not possible. Slow innovation adoption cripples institutions and increases the level of innovator dropouts.

Infrastructure support - Europe is more developed in terms of innovation infrastructure enablers such as internet connectivity, reliable power supplies and access to raw materials. Africa has a concentration of these technologies in the urban setup. This defines the mapping of innovations in the respective continents, where Europe has a more even distribution in all parts.

Case: 'Innovation in Ghana is concentrated in Accra the capital city and Kumasi. In Kenya, the innovation is concentrated in Nairobi (the capital), Kisumu and Mombasa. In Germany, there is an even distribution in both west and east Germany with reputable organizations in all areas.'

Access to devices and basic components for innovation is a challenge in most African countries. The available devices are also scarce and either outdated or an old version. The European case has a variety of the devices and often new versions are available for the innovators to consume.

Case: 'The [HUBiquitous](#) initiative worked with innovators in Africa. Challenges of device and component access were reported. Also, logistical challenges of the components in each of the countries was experienced with each planned delivery taking a considerable amount or not receiving the shipment. The components were easily available in Germany as the coordinating country.'

Limited number of Innovation hubs. Facilities such as learning and lab facilities for innovation is a challenge. While Africa has over [600 Digital Innovation Hubs](#), they are still not sufficient to serve the available population of researchers. The available facilities are often in most cases either limited in activities or abandoned as shells due to difficulty in resource access. Collaboration amongst the innovation hubs is also often complex leading the institutions working in silos. The definition of innovation hubs in Europe is different and often well managed.

Case: 'Hubs in the Congo Republic depend on the border hubs in Rwanda for equipment and other other sources. The Full development agency in Congo is the only hub available in a location with over 2 million people.'

Differences in Infrastructure leads to differences in the innovation levels between the two continents. Access to devices and components to build and develop determines the quality of

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innovations. The research facility per innovator ratio determines the number of innovators and innovations per region.

Inclusivity and empowerment - This involves access to services by marginalized communities and groups. Mostly, these groups involve women and youth and remote communities. This challenge should answer the question of how to encourage most women and youth participation in digital initiatives. It also should provide solutions of how to trickle the given solutions to communities in remote locations. Most initiatives are often concentrated in the urban areas and are dominated by the male gender.

Intellectual property awareness and funding support – Many innovators have great ideas. They also have the skill required to develop high quality innovations. In cases where additional support is required, they find experts to work with to realize the innovation and further consult relevant institutions such as their hubs, the universities and relevant public and private organizations. Most of these innovators are eventually exploited by the experts and organizations because the intellectual property of the innovation was ignored or not adhered to from the beginning. Most innovators end up giving up due to this.

Case 1: 'The origins of M-PESA are still very unclear with some sources crediting it to Nick Hughes and other sources to Nyagaka Anyona Ouko, a third-year student at Moi University. [Other sources provide credit to specific contributions by each of them](#) independently. If the IP configuration was clear from the inception of the idea then ownership would also be clear.'

Case 2: 'Universities in Kenya also have a policy that 10 percent of the royalties of any innovations initiated from the University belong to the University.'

Alignment of IP policies between the European and African Researchers

Hypothesis: 'If there is promotion of IP and IP management policies, strategies and tools through funding of R&I innovations directed to the collaborative AU-EU framework, then we would have the same level of protection and required standard of ideas and solutions from both continents and thus the ease of exchanging ideas between the two continents'.

This Eliminates fear of exchanging ideas, brings alignment in the quality required for R&I research with potential for high level research, provides a protection membrane for R&I solutions co-developed by partners across the AU-EU and creates awareness on the need and process for IP management throughout an R&I project execution process (IP admins). Good ideas from the low-and-middle income countries in Africa are protected, for example M-pesa.

Awareness of IP Management strategies, techniques and tools for entrepreneurs through training programs.

Hypothesis: 'There is a challenge in direction of funding resources and influence/decision making towards development of IP management training courses and modules. The right players are not sitting on the decision-making table'

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More professionals will be available to identify, manage and commercialize IP assets. Higher impact and higher quality solutions due to the high rate of market commercialization. Awareness of IP management techniques, processes and benefits by aspiring entrepreneurs

Higher collaboration rate among researchers due to the economic value.

Africa to EU mobility challenges - It is easier to get a VISA while travelling from Europe to Africa but a very complex and long process for the vice versa. While the political and security reasons are understood, it has often been surprising that European led initiatives are affected by this situation also. [Over 30 percent of researchers](#) from Africa are denied travel VISAs due to the long and tedious process involved in the VISA processing for Africa.

Case: "Partner meetings for AU-EU innovation projects that take place in Europe are attended by a few African partners due to VISA challenges."

2.2 Local Gaps

The african ecosystem gaps were assessed in the context the the four pilot regions where SEADE is implemented including Senegal, Ghana, Kenya and South Africa. These gaps that apply specifically to the local ecosystem assessed in relation to the European Union R&I collaboration activities. These are summarized below.

Ghana

Mentorship programs - Structured mentorship programmes for innovators (the startup journey, product development, applications for funding)

"Limited Access to mentorship and advisory services is crucial. Startups need guidance beyond just funding." This was the parting shot from one of the established founders from MEST Africa during the interview process for the needs assessment in Ghana. Mentorship is critical for Business development, market entry, regulatory compliance, and scaling strategies. The claim is due to limited structured programs to support start-ups and innovators on their solution development journey. They lack the visibility of early-stage challenges and sustainable planning for their development.

Kenya

Limited Awareness of R&I Development Opportunities - Innovators and DIHs have no knowledge of various digital innovation opportunities

Kenya is at the center of digital transformation in East Africa. Often considered as the silicon savanna or the digital hub of East Africa, Kenya enjoys a vast number of opportunities, investments and a test bed of new technologies and initiatives. Regardless, this is concentrated in the capital. The outskirts of Nairobi, including other major cities and towns do not receive the same type of exposure. These opportunities and initiatives are not easily visible in these cities

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and towns. A notable example is through the workshops conducted under SEADE which involved innovators from the outskirts of Nairobi. A conversation with them demonstrated that they were not aware of many of the digital activities that happen in the capital including simple awareness items as digital events. The realization is that, opportunities are available but the information does not go beyond the capital.

Senegal

Market Linkages - Strengthening market linkages for digital innovations

This involves the ease of transitioning a product to the market. The lack of clear guidelines and support structures for regulatory compliance poses significant challenges for entrepreneurs attempting to scale their businesses locally and internationally. Moreover, startups often face barriers to entry in foreign markets due to limited knowledge of export procedures, trade regulations, and market dynamics. Below are the recommendations:

South Africa

Unequal Power Dynamics - Equitable partnership frameworks to balance power dynamics

This involves inequality in decision making. Institutions may feel underrepresented or overshadowed in these projects, impacting the equality and effectiveness of partnerships. Traditional leaders and elders hold substantial influence in decision-making within their communities. These leaders act as gatekeepers to innovation, meaning that their support or opposition can determine whether new technologies are accepted or rejected. Innovators must navigate these local power dynamics carefully, often needing to engage with elders and other influential figures to gain community approval for their solutions. Some recommendations include:

Generally, the findings from research show this distinction between global and local gaps. There are seven main global gaps that stood out and they included; cultural and operational differences, funding for innovators, policy and legal barriers, infrastructure support, inclusivity and empowerment, intellectual property awareness and support, and Africa to Europe mobility challenges. Country specific challenges included; for Ghana, mentorship programs, for Kenya, Limited awareness of R&I opportunities, for Senegal, Market Linkages and for South Africa, unequal power dynamics. This section provided a good understanding of the challenges with recognition that the challenges are not new. Effort has been put over time to improve them, and this report merely provides additional ideas, opinions and recommendations of solving them. The recommendations are well formulated and explained in the next section.

3. Policy Position

The following section will provide recommendations to the gaps identified. The analysis in the gaps section will guide the construction of the recommendations with suitable explanations for each. Below, all the gaps are listed with their suitable recommendations.

Cultural and Operational Differences.

There have been cases where the solution is implemented in a certain community, and it works but transferring the same solution in a neighbouring community directly becomes a challenge. It is not immediately accepted. This has often led to additional challenges of difficulties in scalability of a solution following its initial deployment. Several innovators have seen the need to rephrase the term **‘human-centered design’** to **‘community centered design’**. The following is recommended:

Intercultural training and inclusive communication strategies - Cultural and contextual differences between the AU and EU regions can sometimes pose challenges to effective collaboration. Understanding and respecting these differences are crucial for successful partnerships. Incorporating cultural sensitivity and contextual understanding into collaborative projects is essential. Intercultural training programs and inclusive communication strategies should be integral parts of AU-EU collaborations to foster mutual respect and understanding.

Adopting objectives from The African Union strategy for gender equality and women empowerment which include:

- Promote women and girls' access to ICT and STEM education
- Ensure the participation of women in the digital economy and ICT-related careers
- Address and eliminate gender-based digital divides
- Enhance the safety and security of women and girls online

Some of the initiatives to resolve these challenges include:

- Curriculum Integration designed to be inclusive and accessible, particularly among women, youth, and in rural areas.
- Teacher and Trainer Empowerment emphasizing pedagogical approaches suited to digital education.
- Online Learning Platforms and Resources that cater to a range of skills and competencies.
- Community Digital Hubs especially in underserved and rural areas, to provide access to digital learning resources and connectivity.

Digital Inclusion - the government must continually seek mechanisms to foster economic inclusion and bridge the gap between the rich and poor. Digital inclusion through affordable connectivity, data, and digital technology access is vital for achieving these goals, especially for small, medium, and micro enterprises (SMMEs) and startups, which have the potential to create

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jobs and contribute to economic growth. Digital inclusion should also focus on the indigent, the youth, women and people with disability to enable them, not only to be able to access government services, but to also have access to data and internet connectivity to enable them to innovate and develop digitally tradable goods and services necessary to ensure their economic inclusion.

Tech to fit communities not communities to fit tech - Need for tech to recognize that communities have evolved solutions to many of their problems. Tech needs to work with the evolutionary process rather than trying to reshape it or, even, to impose its own process

Related Initiatives: FPI project 'Open Internet in Africa' (ECOSOLVE - Innovative solutions against environmental crime, EU Global Facility on Anti-Money Laundering and Countering the Financing of Terrorism, EU Policy and Outreach Partnerships, Support to the Oslo Action Plan of the Ottawa Convention, Global Exchange on Religion in Society, Cultural Relations Platform, Social Media 4 Peace, Promoting the role of women in security and counterterrorism, Open Internet Africa), Human-Centered Digitisation Initiative in Kenya

Funding for innovators

Incorporation of a more realistic Resource Mobilization strategy the development MasterPlan - A more realistic resource mobilization strategy needs to be incorporated in the Master Plan to address the issues of finances, time, systems/tools and human capital. The region needs to have a policy on resource mobilization for the master plan.

Simpler Application Processes – While startups and early-stage innovators are high risk borrowers, it would still be of interest to develop processes that enable them to access funding with ease. While the measures put in place are meant to guarantee a high level of success, on the other hand, it discourages many young innovators who would otherwise be successful after several attempts on their development. There is a higher chance of increasing the success rate by allowing easier process for funding applications.

'Brokers' for funding applications – There is need for intermediaries to support innovators to apply for available funding opportunities. While the process for applications is a learning experience for the innovators, it may be important to **"let the innovators be innovators"** and funding be supported by a separate entity. The kind of approach ensures specialization in the development of the solution with high probability of advanced developments

Innovators and Hubs – A call to all innovators especially the early-stage innovators to work with hubs in their vicinity as opposed to working in silos. Hubs should also be the link to funding opportunities and include programs that teach and support the innovators to apply for funding. This kind of support should be regenerative in the sense that successful innovators can come back and mentor the new innovators on funding opportunities. It can be termed **'a HighSchool approach to funding opportunities.'**

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Dedicated funding models for Early-Stage Innovators – As early-stage innovators are considered high-risk and often most of them misuse the funding or 99 percent fail due to a lack of proper focus in their objectives, it would still be important to formulate dedicated funding models that suit this kind of behaviour. While 99 percent will fail, the 1 percent may be the difference to an increase in the number of successful innovations leading to companies that would build the economy. Need for support in writing applications - one UK health funder I work with gives very short grants to health professionals (1-3 months) to write applications, for example.

Related initiatives and tools: PRIMA database of Initiatives 300+ initiatives - Farming Systems, Afrifood, Water and WEF, AfricaConnect4 in Sub-Saharan Africa - Capacity Building, secure connectivity, communication, The first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs (AfriConEU), African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem (mAKE), Facilitating and stimulating the unleashing of innovation potential through the first Pan EU-Africa sustainable network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) focussing on smart logistic.(DIGILOGIC), “Innovation Dialogues Europe-Africa” D4D Hub (IDEA D4D Hub), African-European Digital Innovation Bridge Network (AEDIB|NET), Catalytic Africa

Policy and Legal Barriers

Bureaucorruption notice – The red-tape among organizations that curtail the process of access to services for innovators should be put on notice. The persons causing the delays should also be put on notice. Institutions should clearly and openly provoke this conservation and take it as seriously as corruption is dealt with in these institutions.

Dedicated guidelines for Innovator processes – It should be a directive for all organizations and institutions to clearly outline processes that innovators should follow to access various services. These services will include funding received via the institution, intellectual property services, mentorship etc.

Let innovators own their products and services – Institutions should lift the percentage ownership criteria and focus on proposing a model of working with the innovators that would be a win-win situation for both. **Partnerships as opposed to Mandatory partial ownership.**

Related initiatives and tools: BMZ digital Global initiatives, scaling impact in international cooperation, management monitoring and verification of digital projects, ICT readiness information tool, detection project potential and risks assessment tool

Infrastructure support

Differences in Infrastructure leads to differences in the innovation levels between the two continents. Access to devices and components to build and develop determines the quality of

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innovations. The research facility per innovator ratio determines the number of innovators and innovations per region.

Support of connectivity and Utilization Technologies - Connectivity and utilisation of technologies should be supported by a reliable energy supply. South Africa has over time experienced energy supply challenges which has had a negative impact on government and industrial initiatives to grow the economy and foster economic inclusion. The functionality of most of the digital infrastructure relies significantly on reliable energy supply. Data centres also rely significantly on cooling systems that require vast volumes of water. In addition to energy supply challenges, issues of sustainability are beginning to take centre stage.

Strengthening Digital Infrastructures: Continue investing in telecommunications infrastructures, including fiber optics and submarine cables, to enhance national and international connectivity.

African Digital Compact recommendations - addressed through the pillar 2 of the African Digital Compact. Investment Priority: Accelerate investments in the development and modernization of digital infrastructure. This includes the expansion of broadband networks, the establishment of data centres, and the deployment of 5G technology to enhance connectivity and digital service delivery

Related Initiatives and tools - Paving the Foundation for Disruptive Technologies in Tomorrow's Digital Innovation Hubs (HUBiquoteous) through the WaziLab platform, EurAfrica Gateway cable - Medusa Flagship (Senegal), Connected Economy and Society (Egypt), Global Maritime Technology Cooperation Centres (phase 2), Sustainable Aviation Fuels, Olkaria I & IV Upgrading project in Kenya, Transfer of innovative Polish biogas technology to the agricultural sector in Kenya, Zambia – Tanzania – Kenya (ZTK) Interconnector, Construction of Kakono Hydropower Plant in Tanzania, Critical raw materials (CRM) Partnership Roadmap in Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia, Msimbazi Basin Development Project in Tanzania, Solar power plant Kaleo in Ghana, Rehabilitation feeder and farm roads in Ghana, Irrigation programme PARIIS and rural development programme PADAER II in Senegal, Just Energy Transition Partnership in Senegal, Cleanup of Hann Bay (Dakar) in Senegal, Casamance project: upgrade and operation of the port of Ziguinchor in Senegal, Construction of Bus Rapid Transit system in Dakar, Senegal, Development of Dakar Bus Public Transport Network in Senegal, Rehabilitation of the road Bissau/Safim - Mpack/Senegal border (115 km), Guinea Bissau, Bio2Watt plants expansion in South Africa: producing biogas from animal waste and other waste sources, Financial platforms for green hydrogen in South Africa and Namibia, Just Energy Transition Partnership in South Africa

Inclusivity and empowerment

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Low number of women, youth and marginalized communities accessing digital opportunities. Below are some of the recommendations.

I am safe, my data is safe – the digital safety of children, women and youth is often not properly considered. Content developed is any content and it affects children, women and youth is not considered. Pillar 6 of the African Digital Compact: Enhancement of Cybersecurity and Data Protection provides recommendations for cybersecurity through Strategic initiatives such as: Cybersecurity and Trust, Legislative and Regulatory Frameworks, conforming to protection of Peace, Stability and Good Governance, Capacity Building and awareness, collaboration and partnerships, Innovation technology and development, Standards and best practices.

Starting from the root – where culture affects access of services or opportunities to women and youth, targeted educational programs can come in to support community leaders to reach out to parents and individuals with high opinion against the participation of women and youth in certain opportunities.

Gender bias and work-life balance - Expanding digital literacy programs and creating more inclusive work environments in the tech and innovation sectors are essential for fostering a vibrant and equitable ecosystem

Related Initiatives and tools: Global partnership for Education, Investing in Young Businesses in Africa, Regional Teachers Initiative for Africa, Youth Mobility for Africa, Gender Transformative Action in Tanzania - Education and Research, AU-EU Innovation Agenda = 87 sub-initiatives.

Intellectual property awareness and support

Allocate European funding for IP management in less advanced African countries/regions. This initiative would benefit multiple African regions, establish an efficient framework for EU-Africa collaboration, and ensure sustainability of innovation-strengthening initiatives between the continents. Such a measure would provide a crucial foundation for effective cooperation, fostering long-term development of innovations between the EU and Africa.

Strengthen capacity building with training programs for aspiring entrepreneurs. The policy makers should facilitate that by giving more funding or involve Higher Education decision makers to the table. This initiative should encompass intellectual property concepts, ethics, stakeholder management and engagement, and inclusiveness. By integrating these elements, the program will facilitate co-creation between African entrepreneurs and local communities, fostering sustainable and culturally relevant innovation.

Fund projects that train IP agents, lawyers, and business owners to better understand and navigate the IP system. WIPO plays a major role in capacity building and offers various free e-learning courses through the WIPO Academy.

The European Patent Office (EPO) provides e-learning resources and collaborates with institutions like CEIPI on IP management education

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Related Initiatives: Horizon Europe African Initiative III - Objectives that link to the IP management in ‘Innovation and Technology’ and ‘Capacity of Science’ pillars, AfrIPI - Improving IP protection, Providing IP management training for SMEs - Enhancing SMEs

Africa to EU mobility challenges

For ease of mobility, exceptions can be introduced that allow expedited VISAs for researchers. Despite the need for political and security checks, innovators can be given priority over other reasons such as tourist cases.

Related Initiatives and tools: Startup Act in SA

Mentorship programs

Borrowing from Kenya and Senegal youth mentorship programmes- Benchmarking with the annual youth mentorship program for ICT professionals in Kenya - through ECOWAS, several strategies defined in the Kenya Digital Masterplan 2022-2032 on the annual youth mentorship program can be adapted. Caption as from the [Kenya Digital Masterplan](#):

From Senegal’s ‘Digital Senegal 2025 Strategy’, Public-Private Partnerships: Develop collaborations with the private sector to create FabLabs and other innovation structures in regional capitals, thus supporting the country's digital entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Industry partnerships - creation of an easy environment for innovators to access industrial environments. Initiatives to encourage industries to create awareness programmes for their activities, direct application and adoption of innovators’ ideas and ease of formation of partnerships and meaningful collaborations.

“Networking platforms that provide invaluable advice, feedback, and support for businesses as they navigate regulatory challenges and scale their operations.”

Dedicated programs for Women and Youth - While this falls under inclusivity also, it is important to also describe it here as women and youth need women and youth success figures to provide motivation, direction and consistency in the innovation activities that they do.

“The structured programs from recommendations 1 and the industry participation from recommendation 2 should include women and youth leaders that can be embraced by the innovators”

Identification of proper institutions to be the channel of access of such mentorship programs - Incubators, Accelerators, TechHubs, general workspaces, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), Makerspaces etc, which one is it? Which is the proper channel for interfacing innovators to supply the mentorship programs?

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“What works as an institution for Ghana? How can the mentorship programs be delivered to the innovators?”

This must be identified properly to ensure that the right target is met and a large scale of innovators is reached.

Role of the EU - For EU related integrations, mentorship should be provided at this level also. For innovators that seek to cooperate or collaborate with EU startups and innovators dedicated sessions can be integrated to the mentorship programs to guide on the process of integration, manage expectations and ease the path to the collaborations.

“Local EU institutions can be the proper/easier linkage to provide this support.”

Related Initiatives and tools: BIC Africa, Investing in Young Businesses in Africa, Youth Mobility for Africa, AfricaConnect4 in Sub-Saharan Africa, BMZ digital political initiatives, Alignment of R&I policies

Policies exist but they do not integrate properly with national policies, regional policies like ECOWAS policies and international policies. The ICT policy in Ghana is not well formulated. The ECOWAS policy on ICT is well developed. Policies enable the set-up of local government structures that serve its people better. A directive can be generated from the ECOWAS level but then transfer at the local level becomes difficult since there are no proper supporting structures to handle the directives. Local innovations are therefore not matched properly with the requirements for the regional level and thus the international level. Below are some of the recommendations to solve this problem.

Limited Awareness of R&I Development Opportunities

Diversification of the test environments - launching of digital initiatives in other cities and towns aside from the capital. This will involve the identification of active innovation hubs or Research and Innovation institutions and working with them to implement several initiatives. This can also be channeled through several relevant institutions in those cities or towns.

“Move out of the capital. Implement the programs in the regions beyond the capital.”

Related Initiatives: AfricaConnect4 in Sub-Saharan Africa - - infrastructure and e-services, - Moodle,- Eduroam, - Videoconferencing, - identity federation, - open science platforms,- cybersecurity

Use of the common channels of communication for Innovators - While mainstream platforms such as LinkedIn, Email communications, newsletters and press releases are professional and considered the official channels of communication, this is not the common channel used by Innovators. By working with innovators to understand how they receive information, the same

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channels can be used to transfer new initiatives and opportunities that can be beneficial for the researchers.

“Learn how the innovators communicate and adapt to those communication channels”

Brief Motivational Programs and Resources - formulating brief motivational programs that encourage innovators to access and follow through in the participation of the available opportunities. As student innovators often have limited time to access and work on several activities due to their focus on studies, motivating them to participate in the programs and making it brief and concise would help them access the information easily and increase the number of participants to several digital opportunities.

“Motivate the innovators”

Market Linkages

Comprehensive market research and validation processes - Addressing the route-to-market challenges requires several targeted strategies. Innovators need comprehensive market research and validation processes to ensure products meet market demands.

Incremental scaling—growing operations based on demand and customer feedback—can mitigate financial risks.

Establishing strategic partnerships with industry players and investors can provide the necessary resources and expertise for startups to navigate complex regulatory environments and achieve market success.

Investments in supporting infrastructure, such as business incubators and IoT labs, are critical to enabling the transition from research to market-ready products.

Simplifying regulatory compliance through mentorship and advisory services will also help innovators navigate bureaucratic hurdles more efficiently.

Related Initiatives and tools: AfricaConnect4 in Sub-Saharan Africa - Capacity Building, secure connectivity, communication, AU-EU Data Flagship - - engagement on Policy, Knowledge sharing, Contribution to Innovations

Unequal Power Dynamics

Involving Community Leaders - engagement of community leaders and other influential leaders during solution development and implementation. This will provide a general understanding of the solution by the community and include a sense of ownership in the solution.

Ensuring adequate regulatory frameworks - addressed through the pillar 2 of the African Digital Compact and the drafting and building of the Startup Act in SA. To develop and implement policy and regulatory frameworks that encourage investment in digital infrastructure. This involves the formulation of clear guidelines for public-private partnerships (PPPs) and incentives for private sector investments in infrastructure projects. Addressed in other pillars also.

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Related Initiatives and tools: Team Europe Initiative on Data Governance in Africa, BMZ digital Global initiatives (scaling impact in international cooperation, management monitoring and verification of digital projects, ICT readiness information tool, detection project potential and risks assessment tool, The Startup Act in SA.

4. Conclusion

The challenges for the Europe – Africa cooperation on digital Research and Innovation are many. Project capacity constraints limit the depth and expanse in which these challenges can be tackled conclusively. It otherwise provides a platform for highlighting these issues which could be addressed in part by other initiatives. The novelty of this report is the proper understanding of the challenges rather in their general format, for example, literacy for applying for funding rather than access to funding as a challenge. The reader therefore gets the proper context and state of the problem and can relate to the recommendations.

5. Annexes

Results of the policies and strategies collected

Number of policies and Strategies and Trade and Industry related

Results of the interviews conducted

34 organisations in total

Institutions Reached

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Results of the surveys deployed

221 persons interviewed. Example questions and responses as below.

Do the current policies in my country adequately support research and innovation in the digital ecosystem?

There is sufficient funding available for digital innovation projects in my country.

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Collaboration between government agencies and local stakeholders is effective in promoting digital innovation

Results of the initiatives collected

Ghana, Kenya, Senegal, South Africa and EU-SSA

Key database for Initiatives

1. The global gateway

2. D4D hub

Who we are ▾

What we do

Initiatives

The D4D Hub's work facilitating coordination and collaboration h

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3. Dashboard of Initiatives

Type of Action

- Short-term (until 2026)
- Medium-term (until 2030)
- Long-term (until 2033)

Priority areas

- Public Health
- Green Transition
- Innovation & Technology
- Capacities for Science
- Cross-cutting issues

Search for initiative(s)

*To look for more than one initiative, please use a comma "," to separate each initiative's name.

Search for funding and/or implementing entity

Dashboard of initiatives contributing to the implementa

Click on each initiative's cell to access to its respective website. By leaving your mouse on each budget line, a summary t

Type of Action: All

Priority areas	Action title	Initiative	Month/Year of Start	Month/Year of End
Public Health	Designing and implementing new methods and tools to monitor, prevent and counteract future health threats (long standing/re-emerging/antimicrobial resistant pathogens as well as chronic diseases), promoting One Health and precision medicine, in a changing environment, embedding the mental health dimension in this approach	HENDDU Action Plan	May 2024	April 2025
		Project Green Initiative	February 2017	December 2021

4. The African Union

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